

Evaluation of Relationships Between Agro-Morphological Traits in Barley Genotypes

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the morphological and agronomic traits of nine barley genotypes under environmental conditions of Kahramanmaraş, Türkiye and to assess the potential use of these traits as adaptation and selection criteria and the relationships among them. The experiments were conducted in the Eastern Mediterranean region of Türkiye over two consecutive years (2014-2016), using a randomised complete block design with three replications. Plant height (93.0-106.7 cm), spike length (7.1-10.8 cm), peduncle length (20.2-28.0 cm), flag leaf length (9.7-13.3 cm), flag leaf width (0.95-1.30 cm), number of spikes per square meter (366.6-542.7 spikes/m²), grain weight per spike (1.07-1.72 g), grain number per spike (21.2-48.0 splices), harvest index (21.5-36.6 %), biomass yield (1282.2-1811.8 kg da⁻¹) and protein yield (50.2-72.9 kg da⁻¹). According to the results, the relationships between genotypes in barley were analyzed and their contribution to genetic studies was presented.

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1. Introduction

Cereals, the primary source of carbohydrates in the human diet, were among the first domesticated plants to be cultivated and show a wide variety of species, varieties and ecotypes (Kün, 1996). Archaeological findings reveal that barley was cultivated in Iran around 8000 BC. Barley and oats have the highest beta-glucan concentration among all grains (Sullivan et al., 2013; Anonymous, 2023). The cultivation area of barley in the world is approximately 49 million hectares and the global production is 146.6 million tons. The world average yield is 3270 kg ha⁻¹. Russia ranks first in the world with 18 million tons of production, Australia ranks second with 14.6 million tons and France ranks third with 11.3 million tons (FAO, 2022). In Türkiye, barley cultivation area is 31 million da, production is 8.5 million tons and yield is 266 kg da⁻¹ (Anonymous, 2022). Barley, once a staple in human diets, is now primarily cultivated for two purposes in the world and in Türkiye: as a feed for animal nutrition and for malt-beer production in the industry (Kılınç et al., 1992). It has been reported that the most important thing in plant breeding programs is to provide increases in yield potential and that cereal yield can be broken down into components such as number of plants per unit area, number of spikes per plant, grain number per spike and grain weight per spike are accepted as criteria for achieving high yield (Hsu and Walton, 1971). Genetic richness was discovered among local barley populations under similar climatic conditions in Syria and Jordan (Fertile Crescent). By examining the agronomic, morphological and quality characteristics of the spikes collected from local barley varieties, it was stated that this material can be used in breeding programs by identifying single spike progenies with better agronomic characteristics than the original local varieties and with good yield, creating pure lines, using them in hybrid programs

and using them in pure line mixtures (Ceccarelli et al., 1987). Excessive use of chemicals such as pesticides, herbicides and fungicides, environmental conditions, green revolution, diseases, fertilization, irrigation and yield relationship between varieties were examined and it was determined that plant height, physiological and agronomic characters affect yield (Evans et al., 1999). This study aimed to determine the relationships between morphological and agronomic traits in different barley varieties under Kahramanmaraş conditions.

2. Material and Methods

In this research, direct and indirect effects of all traits on grain yield were determined by investigating the relationships between the characters examined using correlation and path analysis with 9 genotypes belonging to the barley genus in 2014-2015 and 2015-2016 growing years under Kahramanmaraş conditions and it was sown as a winter crop with 3 replications according to the randomized complete block design. Maintenance operations (weed control, fertilization) were carried out according to the development status of the plant, taking into account the prevailing climatic conditions. Sowing was carried out with a 6-row plot seeder with a row spacing of 20 cm on plots 8.30 meters in length, with a sowing density of 400 seeds per m² in barley. Sowing depth was 3-4 cm and plot size was 1.2mx8.3m = 9.96 m². Fertilization was completed in both years by applying commercial fertilizer 20-20-0 (compound) at 7 kg da⁻¹ pure N and 7 kg pure P₂O₅ as base fertilizer at sowing and 33 % ammonium nitrate (NH₄NO₃) at 7 kg ha⁻¹ pure N at the end of tillering. No irrigation was applied in the study, which was conducted solely based on rainfall. Weed control was performed using a selective herbicide (2,4-D Amine). In the soil of the study area, phosphorus and potassium among macro plant nutrients are moderately

sufficient, calcium and magnesium are present in excess. Micronutrients except manganese are low or insufficient. Organic matter content is low, lime content is high, and the soil is slightly alkaline (Anonymous, 2015). The region has a Mediterranean characterized by significant seasonal temperature differences, with mild and rainy winters and hot, dry summers. The year 2015-2016 was drier and hotter and with lower average relative humidity compared to 2014–2015. According to the

long-term average, total precipitation (mm) was higher especially in December, April and June, 2014-2015 received more precipitation than the long-term data, while the total amount of precipitation determined in 2015-2016 was below the long-term average. When we look at the average temperature data, it was determined that the average temperature was above the long-term average in both growing periods, especially in March, April, May and June.

Table 1. Graph of climate characteristics data for trial years

Months	Total rainfall (mm)		Average temperature (°C)		Average relative humidity (%)	
	2014-2015	2015-2016	2014-2015	2015-2016	2014-2015	2015-2016
December	108.6	20.0	10.5	8.9	70.8	44.9
January	173.6	140.6	6.4	4.3	65.8	64.6
February	207.4	30.3	8.5	11.2	68.9	59.9
March	183.0	61.3	12.7	13.2	55.0	50.1
April	62.6	17.6	16.5	21.6	47.9	32.6
May	63.8	16.5	24.2	21.1	37.9	48.1
June	1.0	0.59	27.7	28.4	36.9	37.1
Average	114.2	40.9	15.2	15.5	54.7	48.1

Considering the 2-year growing season (Table 1), the coldest month was January, the hottest month was June and January was the month with the highest average relative humidity and the highest rainfall in both years (Anonymous, 2016a). When the average relative humidity (%) data of the long-term averages and 2-year growing periods were compared, it was observed that the average relative humidity (%) values were below the long-term average in both years, especially in January, March, April, May and June (Anonymous, 2016b). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using the SAS software package (SAS, 1999), and mean comparisons were made with Duncan's multiple range test. The methods used by Bares et al. (1985) were modified and used for the evaluation of the studied traits. Measurements and observations were conducted according to developmental stages using Zadoks Scale (ZD). Plant measurements and yield values were calculated following the Technical

Instructions for Agricultural Values Measurement Trials by the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock (Anonymous, 2008).

3. Results and Discussion

As a result of the evaluation of the genotypes considering the two-year averages in terms of the traits examined, it was determined that the genotypes were significantly different in terms of plant height, spike height, peduncle length, flag leaf length, flag leaf width, number of spikes per square meter, grain weight per spike, grain number per spike, harvest index, biomass yield and protein yield. Phenotypical correlation analysis was used, so it can be meaningful even at low values. According to the results of correlation analysis, there was a positive and very significant relationship between peduncle length and plant height (Table 2). Similar to this study, negative and significant relationships were determined between

number of spikes per square meter and grain number per spike under dry and irrigated conditions in Konya with different cereal species (Küçükakça, 1995). In the study, positive and very significant correlations

were found between grain weight and grain number per spike (Table 2). In another study, a positive correlation was found between grain weight and grain number per spike (Semiz, 2021).

Table 2. Correlation coefficients of examined traits of the genotypes as an averages of two years of the study

Traits	PY	PH	SL	PL	FLW	FLL	SN	GNS	GWS	BIO	HI
PY	1										
PH	-0.419**	1									
SL	0.021	0.196	1								
PL	-0.543**	0.602**	0.171	1							
FLW	-0.495**	0.224	-0.202	0.119	1						
FLL	-0.349**	0.258	-0.013	0.030	0.462**	1					
SN	-0.511**	0.403**	-0.052	0.400**	0.129	0.310*	1				
GNS	0.233	-0.282*	-0.397**	-0.366**	0.107	-0.073	-0.308*	1			
GWS	0.508**	-0.381**	-0.106	-0.510**	-0.008	-0.222	-0.601**	0.752**	1		
BIO	0.497**	-0.455**	-0.307*	-0.203	-0.202	-0.197	-0.357**	0.281*	0.318*	1	
HI	0.559**	-0.122	0.209	-0.510**	-0.218	-0.171	-0.296*	0.128	0.340*	-0.355**	1

*Significant at 5 % level, **Significant at 1 % level. PY= protein yield, PH= plant height, SL= spike length, PL=peduncle length, FLW=flag leaf width, FLL=flag leaf length, SN= number of spikes per square meter, GNS=grain number per spike, GWS=grain weight per spike, BIO=biomass yield, HI=harvest index

When the average of two years was analyzed, the highest plant height value was obtained from Sur-93 genotype with 106.7 cm, while the lowest value was obtained from Eralam*Yabani genotype with 93.0 cm (Table 3). In a study conducted with 25 barley varieties under Kahramanmaraş and Şanlıurfa conditions, it was found that the varieties differed significantly in terms of plant height and plant height ranged between 55.98-110.8 cm (Çölkesen et al. (2002). In barley, plant height of 30-35 cm is called dwarf, 120 cm and above is called extremely tall and it is stated that the varieties with plant height between 80 and 100 cm and longer (>100 cm) are generally grown in the Transcaucasian, Far East, West, South and South - West Europe in humid and warm regions. Short plants as endemic forms can be found in the hot and dry regions of Central and South-West Asia and North Africa or in the humid and hot climates of China and Japan (Von Bothmer et al., 2003). Especially in regions with high rainfall and fertile soils, tall varieties are easily lodged and as a result, yield and quality decrease and harvesting becomes difficult and harvest losses increase (Kün, 1996) and similar findings have been

observed in this study. In a study where 12 different varieties were used in Diyarbakır and Adıyaman locations, plant heights were found to vary between 76.7 and 89.7 cm (Çöken and Akman, 2016). In the two-year average, the highest spike length was observed in Sur-93 genotype (10.8 cm) and the lowest value was observed in Kendal genotype (7.1 cm) (Table 3). It was reported that spike length varied between 4.3-9.7 cm in 800 barley materials collected from Southeastern Anatolia region under Diyarbakır conditions (Akıncı and Yıldırım, 2009). As in other quantitative characters, it was determined that spike length was influenced by the time of spike, amount of seed sown per unit area and other environmental conditions in addition to variety characteristics (Akbay, 1970). In another study, spike length was found to be 9.18, 8.68 and 9.75 cm in the first, second and third years, respectively (Roljević Nikolić et al., 2020). Based on the two-years average, the highest the peduncle length was observed in Sur-93 genotype with 28.0 cm and the lowest value was measured in Eralam*Yabani genotype with 20.2 cm (Table 3). In a study on 133 local barley genotypes collected from Pakistan,

the peduncle length was reported to be between 15.9 and 39.1 cm (Ahmad et al., 2008). It was found that barley genotypes

showed an average loss of 21.9% in peduncle length under drought stress conditions (Singh et al., 2015).

Table 3. Results of the investigated traits over two years for plant height, spike length and peduncle length

Genotypes	Plant height (cm)			Spike length (cm)			Peduncle length (cm)		
	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean
Efes-98	96.2 ^C	93.1	94.6 ^{BC}	8.6 ^{CDE}	8.6 ^{CDE}	8.6 ^{BC}	25.8 ^{BC}	18.5	22.2 ^{BC}
Promesa*Yabani	104.3 ^{BC}	90.6	97.5 ^{BC}	11.2 ^A	9.8 ^{AB}	10.5 ^A	26.1 ^{BC}	20.3	23.2 ^{BC}
Şahin-91	104.1 ^{BC}	89.3	96.7 ^{BC}	9.6 ^{ABC}	9.0 ^{BCD}	9.3 ^B	30.9 ^{AB}	21.5	26.2 ^{AB}
Samyeli	102.8 ^{BC}	96.2	99.5 ^{ABC}	9.3 ^{ABCD}	8.4 ^{DE}	8.8 ^B	25.6 ^{BC}	23.8	24.7 ^{AB}
Athena*Yabani	107.2 ^B	97.0	102.1 ^{AB}	9.8 ^{ABC}	9.7 ^{ABC}	9.7 ^{AB}	29.1 ^{ABC}	19.0	24.0 ^{ABC}
Kendal	102.5 ^{BC}	95.9	99.2 ^{ABC}	6.6 ^E	7.5 ^E	7.1 ^D	27.9 ^{BC}	22.6	25.2 ^{AB}
Eralam*Yabani	98.3 ^{BC}	87.8	93.0 ^C	9.0 ^{BCD}	8.8 ^{BCD}	8.9 ^B	24.1 ^C	16.3	20.2 ^C
Altikat	107.4 ^B	88.1	97.8 ^{BC}	7.4 ^{DE}	7.9 ^{DE}	7.6 ^{CD}	23.2 ^C	17.3	20.3 ^C
Sur-93	119.6 ^A	93.9	106.7 ^A	10.9 ^{AB}	10.7 ^A	10.8 ^A	34.5 ^A	21.4	28.0 ^A
Mean	104.7 ^A	92.4	98.6	9.17 ^A	8.9 ^B	9.0	27.5 ^A	20.1	23.8
Mean square	134.706**	38.486	98.852*	6.620**	3.097**	9.027**	37.838**	18.565	40.672**
Coeff var (CV)	4.923	6.792	6.511	11.852	7.123	9.895	11.223	14.214	13.497

The highest value in terms of flag leaf length was observed in Eralam*Yabani genotype with 13.3 cm while the lowest value was observed in Şahin-91 genotype with 9.7 cm (Table 4). It has been reported that environmental conditions have a great effect on the character as well as variety characteristics and flag leaf length has been reported to be greater in six-row barleys than in two-row barleys, varying between 4.0 and 19.3 cm in the latter (Akbat, 1970). Especially under dry conditions, plants with small flag leaves are preferred due to their high photosynthetic efficiency as well as the fact that they reduce competition for

sunlight and allow the formation of a higher number of fertile tillers per unit area (Donald, 1981; Evans, 1981). It was reported that significant decreases (average 30.0 %) in flag leaf length of genotypes occurred under drought stress conditions in barley (Singh et al., 2015). The highest flag leaf width value was observed in Kendal genotype with 1.30 cm and the lowest value was observed in Athena*Yabani genotype with 0.95 cm (Table 4). A study on bread wheat reported that exposure to drought stress caused a decrease in flag leaf width of genotypes ranging from 4.5% to 9.5% (Ayranç, 2012).

Table 4. Results of the investigated traits over two years for flag leaf length and flag leaf width

Genotypes	Flag leaf length (cm)			Flag leaf width (cm)		
	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean
Efes-98	11.6	9.2 ^D	10.4 ^{CD}	1.03	0.9 ^{BC}	0.96 ^C
Promesa*Yabani	14.3	12.4 ^{AB}	13.4 ^A	1.20	1.14 ^A	1.17 ^{AB}
Şahin-91	10.1	9.4 ^D	9.7 ^D	1.17	1.14 ^A	1.15 ^{AB}
Samyeli	12.2	12.5 ^{AB}	12.3 ^{AB}	1.26	0.85 ^C	1.05 ^{BC}
Athena*Yabani	12.0	10.0 ^{CD}	11.0 ^{BCD}	1.05	0.86 ^C	0.95 ^C
Kendal	14.5	11.4 ^{BC}	13.0 ^A	1.36	1.25 ^A	1.30 ^A
Eralam*Yabani	13.0	13.5 ^A	13.3 ^A	1.24	1.16 ^A	1.20 ^{AB}
Altikat	12.6	11.4 ^{BC}	12.0 ^{ABC}	1.23	1.07 ^{ABC}	1.15 ^{AB}
Sur-93	12.4	11.3 ^{BC}	11.8 ^{ABC}	1.19	1.09 ^{AB}	1.14 ^{ABC}
Mean	12.5	11.2 ^B	11.92	1.19	1.05 ^B	1.12
Mean square	5.556	6.523**	9.881**	0.031	0.064**	0.076**
Coeff var (CV)	14.243	9.411	12.099	13.986	11.982	13.103

The highest number of spikes per square meter was observed in Efes-98 genotype (542.7 spikes/m²), while the lowest value was observed in Şahin-91 genotype (366.6 spikes/m²) (Table 5). Drought has a negative effect on some traits of barley. Especially the lack of moisture during tillering period causes a decrease number of spikes per square meter by decreasing the number of tillers per plant (Kırtok and Genç, 1979). It has been reported that barley genotypes have an average of 22% less number of spikes per square meter under drought conditions compared to normal conditions (Hellal et al., 2019). In a study conducted in Diyarbakır and Mardin conditions, the averages number of spikes per square meter were determined as 218 spikes/m² in Diyarbakır (with low rainfall) and 383 spikes/m² in Mardin (with support irrigation) in barley genotypes (Okur ve Aktaş, 2024). The highest value of grain weight per spike was obtained from Altıkat

genotype with 1.72 g, while the lowest value was obtained from Efes-98 genotype with 1.07 g (Table 5). In two-row barley varieties grown in Bafra plain, it was reported that grain weight per spike was range between 1.07-1.16 g (Sirat and Sezer, 2017). The highest grain number per spike was measured in Altıkat genotype (48.0 seeds) and the lowest value was measured in Samyeli genotype (21.2 seeds) (Table 5). In Bafra plain conditions, grain number per spike was ranged between 20.0 and 60.5 in 12 barley varieties, 6 of which were two-rowed and 6 of which were six-rowed (Sirat and Sezer, 2005). In another study, grain number per spike varied between 19-22 seeds and no significant difference was determined according to years and genotypes (Yüksel et al., 2017). In other research, using Güneyyıldızı and Tekin wheat varieties, grain number per spike varied between 29.5 and 33.4 seeds (Daşkın and Alp, 2025).

Table 5. Results of the investigated traits over two years for number of spikes per square, grain weight per spike and grain number per spike

Genotypes	Number of spikes per square meter (spikes/m ²)			Grain weight per spike (g)			Grain number per spike (spices)		
	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean
	Efes-98	731.3	354.1	542.7	0.83 ^B	1.32	1.07 ^C	20.2 ^{BCD}	24.8 ^{BC}
Promesa*Yabani	597.1	282.0	439.5	1.05 ^B	1.57	1.31 ^{BC}	19.4 ^{BCD}	26.6 ^{BC}	23.0 ^{CD}
Şahin-91	430.8	302.5	366.6	1.47 ^A	1.54	1.50 ^{AB}	25.6 ^{BC}	27.2 ^{BC}	26.4 ^C
Samyeli	616.3	374.1	495.2	0.91 ^B	1.27	1.09 ^C	19.0 ^{CD}	23.3 ^C	21.2 ^D
Athens*Yabani	661.7	376.6	519.1	0.93 ^B	1.42	1.17 ^{BC}	23.1 ^{BCD}	26.6 ^{BC}	24.8 ^{CD}
Kendal	617.5	432.9	525.2	0.91 ^B	1.89	1.40 ^{BC}	27.2 ^B	54.0 ^A	40.6 ^B
Eralam*Yabani	530.0	323.7	426.8	0.97 ^B	1.43	1.20 ^{BC}	20.2 ^{BCD}	24.8 ^{BC}	22.5 ^{CD}
Altıkat	519.0	314.1	416.5	1.51 ^A	1.93	1.72 ^A	39.8 ^A	56.2 ^A	48.0 ^A
Sur-93	501.7	325.4	413.5	0.86 ^B	1.57	1.21 ^{BC}	17.6 ^D	32.0 ^B	24.8 ^{CD}
Mean	578.3	342.8	460.6	1.05 ^A	1.55	1.30	23.6 ^A	32.8 ^B	28.2
Mean square	25178.171	6441.203	22573.728	0.198**	0.159	0.267**	141.307**	495.453**	534.035**
Coeff var (CV)	22.547	17.648	21.965	18.703	19.182	19.208	17.270	11.380	13.614

The highest value of harvest index was determined in Eralam*Yabani genotype with 36.6% and the lowest value was determined in Kendal genotype with 21.5% (Table 6). Harvest index was reported to be important for grain yield (Bülbül, 1986). Harvest index is a value found by the ratio of grain yield to biological yield and since

there is an important relationship between grain yield and harvest index, the reason why the harvest index data of Kendal variety was very low in the first year was due to the negative effect of bird damage on grain yield. It was also reported that harvest index was significantly affected by water stress in barley genotypes (Saed-Moucheshi

et al., 2022). The highest value of biomass yield was observed in Kendal genotype with 1811.8 kg da⁻¹ and the lowest value was observed in Sur-93 genotype with 1282.2 kg da⁻¹ (Table 6). Biomass yield was reported to vary between 1136 and 1887 kg da⁻¹ (Dreccer et al., 2009). In terms of protein yield, the highest value was in

Samyeli genotype (72.9 kg da⁻¹) and the lowest value was obtained in Kendal genotype (50.2 kg da⁻¹) (Table 6). Under Van conditions, the highest protein yields were found in Orza-96 variety (55.1 kg da⁻¹), Tokak 157/37, Aday-1 and Ziatko genotypes and the lowest protein yield was found in Lora variety (Akdeniz et al., 2004).

Table 6. Results of the investigated traits over two years for harvest index, biomass yield and protein yield

Genotypes	Harvest index (%)			Biomass yield (kg da ⁻¹)			Protein yield (kg da ⁻¹)		
	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean	2014-15	2015-16	Mean
Efes-98	32.5 ^A	37.7 ^A	35.1	1019.0 ^C	1624.7	1321.8 ^B	45.0 ^A	78.2 ^B	61.6 ^{BCD}
Promesa*Yabani	31.6 ^A	35.9 ^A	33.7	1177.3 ^{BC}	1638.3	1407.8 ^{AB}	41.7 ^A	73.4 ^{BC}	57.6 ^{BCDE}
Şahin-91	33.8 ^A	33.2 ^A	33.5	1267.3 ^{ABC}	1996.7	1632.0 ^{AB}	52.9 ^A	81.1 ^B	67.0 ^{AB}
Samyeli	24.6 ^A	36.2 ^A	30.4	1586.7 ^{AB}	2027.3	1807.0 ^A	46.7 ^A	99.1 ^A	72.9 ^A
Athena*Yabani	29.6 ^A	40.1 ^A	34.8	1275.3 ^{ABC}	1661.0	1468.2 ^{AB}	49.0 ^A	80.3 ^B	64.7 ^{ABC}
Kendal	8.4 ^B	34.6 ^A	21.5	1685.0 ^A	1938.7	1811.8 ^A	19.4 ^B	81.0 ^B	50.2 ^E
Eralam*Yabani	39.2 ^A	33.9 ^A	36.6	1023.7 ^C	1644.0	1333.8 ^B	47.3 ^A	69.7 ^{BC}	58.5 ^{BCDE}
Altukat	30.9 ^A	37.4 ^A	34.1	1217.0 ^{BC}	1569.0	1393.0 ^B	44.4 ^A	61.6 ^C	53.0 ^{DE}
Sur-93	27.1 ^A	36.7 ^A	31.9	1028.7 ^C	1535.7	1282.2 ^B	40.8 ^A	68.7 ^{BC}	54.7 ^{CDE}
Mean	28.6 ^A	36.2 ^B	32.46	1253.3 ^A	1737.2	1495.2	43.0 ^A	77.0 ^A	60.0
Mean square	223.164*	13.367**	119.696	173759.0*	111722.648	252357.782*	275.985**	339.467**	315.714**
Coeff var (CV)	29.520	12.226	23.412	19.041	13.961	20.923	17.101	10.907	12.809

PC1 and PC2 represent 54.8% of the total variation (Figure 1). It is seen that the examined traits are gathered in 4 different groups (Figure 2). In these groups, HI was located alone (A), PY and SL were located (B), PL, PH and SN were located (C), while others formed a separate group (D). Those in group B show significant relationships among themselves, and those in group C also show significant relationships among themselves. In group D, except for biomass yield, the other traits remaining in the group show significant and positive relationships with each other (Figure 2). According to the biplot analysis, when examining the relationships between traits, it was determined that G2 remained in the positive regions and was adaptable to difficult conditions. G6 showed the highest positive values in terms of PC1 and PC2, indicating high performance and adaptability to

favourable environments. G7 and G8 were found to be adaptable to stressful conditions, while the other genotypes (G1, G4, G5 and G9) did not show any special environmental preferences and responded similarly to different environments. It was determined that G4 and G9 exhibited positive characteristics in terms of PL, PH, and SN, while G5 exhibited positive characteristics in terms of PY and SL. It is recommended that these genotypes be used as breeding criteria for the development of related traits (Figure 1). In a study conducted to identify bread wheat varieties suitable for hot stressful conditions, it was noted that varieties close to the center are stable and ideal (Eliş et al., 2024). In this study, the G3 genotype was also determined to be an ideal variety due to its proximity to the center.

Figure 1. Relation among traits over mean of growing seasons

G1: Efes-98, G2: Promesa*Yabani, G3: Şahin-91, G4:Samyeli, G5: Athena*Yabani, G6:Kendal, G7: Eralam*Yabani, G8: Altıkat, G9: Sur-93
 PY= protein yield, PH= plant height, SL= spike length, PL=peduncle length, FLW=flag leaf width, FLL=flag leaf length, SN= number of spikes per square meter, GNS=grain number per spike, GWS=grain weight per spike, BIO=biomass yield, HI=harvest index

Figure 2. Relation between genotypes and traits and grouping of traits over two growing seasons

G1: Efes-98, G2: Promesa*Yabani, G3: Şahin-91, G4:Samyeli, G5: Athena*Yabani, G6:Kendal, G7: Eralam*Yabani, G8: Altıkat, G9: Sur-93
 PY= protein yield, PH= plant height, SL= spike length, PL=peduncle length, FLW=flag leaf width, FLL=flag leaf length, SN= number of spikes per square meter, GNS=grain number per spike, GWS=grain weight per spike, BIO=biomass yield, HI=harvest index

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Eralam*Yabani was one of the highest genotypes in terms of flag leaf width, flag

leaf length and harvest index. Altıkat was the highest variety for grain weight per spike and grain number per spike and

Kendal was the lowest variety about protein yield, harvest index and spike length. Eralam*Yabani and Altıkat genotypes can be recommend for researches and farmers. Genetic structure is manifested in the form of morphological traits such as tillering, spike length and density, grain number per spikelet and grain size. The different reactions of the varieties to the ecological environment and cultural practices lead to varying outcomes across regions (Klapp, 1967; Riggs, 1986). It should be taken into consideration that there are different ecological conditions in both growing periods and varieties respond differently to climatic conditions. It should be known that the genotype to be used may change according to the regions and the traits to be observed (plant height, spike height, peduncle length, flag leaf length, flag leaf width, number of spikes per square meter, grain weight per spike, grain number per spike, harvest index, biomass yield and protein yield) can be used as selection criteria. According to the results of correlation analysis, there is no statistically significant difference. The reason for this is thought to be grain shedding in barley, bird damage, not all varieties are registered and they have different genetic structure. Local varieties that are fully adapted to the ecological conditions of the regions where they grow are the assurance of the future of agriculture and thus of humanity (Özgen et al., 2000). This study will be useful in the development of agricultural production activities and breeding studies by using other locations, different locations and plants and will provide progress in determining the traits to be used.

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